

3 days of
seminars
debates
workshops

to make your

RESEARCH

**visible
transparent
efficient**

PUBLICATION

Open Access
Open Peer Review
Pre-prints
Uploading in Repositories
Monographs and OA

RESEARCH DATA

Best Practices
FAIR Principles
Data Repositories
Data Management Plan
Personal Data

HOT TOPICS

Open Innovation
Patents
Copyright and Licences
Research Evaluation
Publishing Companies

RESEARCH BOOSTERS

Research Visibility
ORCID / DOI
Collaborative Platforms
Digital Notebooks
Social Media

#LuxOSF

<https://openscience2018.uni.lu>

